

SECTION B: THE EFFECTS OF USER-CENTRIC APPROACH (UCA) ON CUSTOMER ACQUISITION, RETENTION, AND SATISFACTION (CARS)

This section contains open questions to collect your opinions about the effect of UCA through its different components, customers acquisition, retention and satisfaction (CARS). Please feel free to share ideas and provide any comments you feel important for the study.

Question 1: What is your impression on how User research and personal development help in improving **customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction (CARS)**?

Question 2: How can you assess the effects of User on boarding experiences on customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction (CARS)?

Question 3: According to you, has the Feedback integration and iterative improvement has impact on customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction (CARS)

Question 4: Do you think continuous customer support on customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction (CARS)?

Question 5: How do different elements of the user-centric approach (UR, UX, FI, and US) collectively affect the overall customer experience in Academic Bridge's SaaS?

Question 6: What challenges does Academic Bridge face in implementing a user-centric approach to improve customer acquisition, retention, and satisfaction?

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION!